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Distinct Metabolic Signatures Associated With Drought Response, Shoot Architecture And Flowering time In Camelina

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36 Drought and Flowering Signatures In Camelina

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53 **Abstract**

54 *Camelina sativa* is an ancient native oilseed species characterized by broad environmental adaptability, low-input
55 requirements and tolerance to multiple stresses. Its potential use in agroecological transition with double
56 cropping systems could be improved by breeding a shorter life cycle. However, this strategy should not
57 compromise its resilience to stresses as well as its metabolite profiles and plasticity. The impact of flowering time
58 on drought stress response and seed quality was evaluated in six camelina edited mutants, carrying combinatory
59 mutations on the flowering time genes *SVP*, *TFL1*, *LHP1*, *ELF3* and *FLC* and leading to a range of flowering
60 precocity and shoot architecture changes. We characterized the phenotype of these mutants in response to early
61 and late drought and showed that their flowering time was not strongly altered contrary to branching and yield.
62 Untargeted metabolomic demonstrated that in contrary to the lipidomic profile, the plasticity of the specialized
63 metabolite was strongly modulated by drought in all genotypes. Specialized metabolite profile of the mutant
64 seeds showed distinct pattern in response to drought with constitutive stress response of the bushy mutants in
65 control condition including differences in antioxidant content such as glutathione, isoquercetrin, and coumaroyl
66 quinic acid. Metabolite profiling in leaves also showed specific metabolic signatures of some mutants but with
67 lower metabolite diversity than in seeds. Including additional genotypes with distinct flowering time, we
68 identified metabolites correlating with this trait, such as vitamin B2 and kynurenic acid in seeds. These
69 metabolites could be used as predictive markers of flowering time.

70

71 **Keywords**

72 Branching, Camelina, Drought response, Flowering time, Seed, Specialized metabolites

73

74 Introduction

75 The diversification of crops associated with a more sustainable cropping system could offer alternative solutions
76 to mitigate climate change and support the agroecological transition. Camelina (*Camelina sativa* (L.) Crantz) is an
77 oilseed crop of the Brassicaceae family producing oil enriched in polyunsaturated fatty acid, specifically the
78 essential omega-3 polyunsaturated alpha-linolenic acid (Zanetti et al., 2021). Besides, camelina seeds
79 accumulated other natural beneficial compounds, including tocopherols (vitamin E) as well as diverse specialized
80 metabolites with antioxidant or antimicrobial activities (Barreda et al., 2025; Boutet et al., 2022; Budin et al.,
81 1995; Quéro et al., 2016). These metabolites are characterized by large structural diversity and functions, and
82 can be categorized into three main classes, namely phenylpropanoids, nitrogen-containing compounds and
83 terpenoids (Barreda et al., 2024). Camelina is also characterized by its low agricultural input requirement and
84 its resilience upon biotic and abiotic stresses and is therefore used in relay cropping or as catch crop (Zanetti et
85 al., 2021). However, its use in double or relay cropping in particular during summer was restricted due to several
86 limitations, mainly late maturity and high occurrence of annual weeds (Leclère et al., 2018). In addition, variable
87 water availability after sowing caused heterogenous seedling emergence. Using camelina as a catch crop would
88 require the improvement of three main traits: (1) its life cycle with early flowering phenotype to allow full seed
89 maturation, (2) its plant architecture with enhanced bushiness to compete with weeds, and (3) its tolerance to
90 drought and heat during the entire life cycle.

91 The fine-tuning of flowering transition determines the timing of seed set and subsequently the reproductive
92 success. The transition from vegetative to reproductive growth is a complex and tightly controlled process that
93 involves a combination of endogenous and environmental signals (Andrés and Coupland, 2012). In the
94 Brassicaceae model plant *Arabidopsis thaliana*, which is closely related to camelina, multiple pathways including
95 vernalization, photoperiod, circadian clock, sugar, age, thermosensory, autonomous, and gibberellin, target
96 integrator genes interconnected in a complex genetic network (Andrés and Coupland, 2012). The regulation of
97 drought stress responses in plants involves also complex signaling networks and flowering time regulators that
98 are known to play a role in coordinating these responses (Kazan and Lyons, 2016). Notably, the flowering
99 repressor SHORT VEGETATIVE PHASE (SVP) confers drought resistance while the mutation of flowering activator
100 *LIKE HETEROCHROMATIN PROTEIN 1 (LHP1)*, showed drought resistance in *Arabidopsis* (Bechtold et al., 2016;
101 Ramirez-Prado et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2018). Inversely, drought strongly impacts several physiological traits
102 including the reduction of plant biomass but also flowering time (Bacelar and Aroca, 2013). Drought induces
103 rapid plant development leading to early flowering in *A. thaliana* and its close related species *Brassica rapa* (Cho
104 et al., 2017; Franks et al., 2007). This strategy, also called drought escape, is often at the expense of plant yield.
105 The trade-off between drought escape and yield may vary among plant species and depend on the specific
106 environmental conditions. For example, studies in wheat have shown that early flowering induced by drought
107 could be favorable for yield (Shavrukov et al., 2017). Conversely, in other species such as rice, maize and quinoa,
108 drought increases the number of days to flower (Abrecht and Carberry, 1993; Fukai, 1999; Geerts et al., 2008).
109 The regulations of seed quality and flowering time are also closely interconnected, as the timing of flowering
110 significantly influences seed development. A direct regulation of various seed traits, including seed size,

111 dormancy, longevity and quality by key flowering regulators have been demonstrated in various plant species.
112 (Nadal Bigas et al., 2025; Ohto et al., 2005; Shoesmith et al., 2021; Soppe et al., 2021; Zhang et al.,
113 2020). Understanding the link and interaction between flowering, drought and seed quality in camelina is
114 essential for developing crops with improved resilience to environmental challenges in the context of climate
115 change.

116 The mechanisms underlying the regulation of flowering time in camelina, as well as its pleiotropic roles in drought
117 stress response and seed quality, remain poorly understood. Genome wide association study (GWAS)
118 demonstrated the high heritability of flowering time in camelina and identified significant trait-associated single
119 nucleotide polymorphisms (Luo Lily et al., 2021). In addition, in camelina one out of four quantitative trait locus
120 (QTL) associated with flowering time overlaps with seed-size-related QTL (Li et al., 2021). Unfortunately, the low
121 genetic diversity of camelina populations associated with its highly redundant hexaploid genome limit the
122 breeding potential of this crop (Kagale et al., 2014). A low-to-moderate predictive ability to improve early
123 flowering traits was observed in camelina (Luo Lily et al., 2021). Using multiplex-editing, a previous study took
124 advantage of the hexaploid genome to obtain a wide range of mutations on the three homoeologs of the
125 flowering repressor genes *FLOWERING LOCUS C (FLC)*, *SVP*, *LHP1*, *TERMINAL FLOWER 1 (TFL1)* and *EARLY*
126 *FLOWERING LOCUS 3 (ELF3)* (Bellec et al., 2022). This strategy induced combinatorial mutations associated with
127 early flowering phenotype, determinate flowering, shorter stature and/or basal branching (Bellec et al., 2022).
128 These *flo*- mutants could therefore represent a valuable genetic background for alternative summer catch crop
129 varieties.

130 To further elucidate the impact of summer cropping on these early flowering *flo*- mutants, we characterized
131 mutant phenotypes in response to early and late drought. We also compared the impact of early and late drought
132 on seed quality and identified different responses across genotypes. Untargeted metabolomic and lipidomic
133 analyses were carried out on seeds to investigate whether flowering mutations could modify seed metabolome
134 profiles upon drought. Our analysis indicates no significant impact of drought on the lipidome contrary to the
135 specialized metabolome in both control and mutants. In addition, in seeds of the bushy *flo*- mutants grown under
136 control conditions, we observed a specialized metabolome associated with drought response. By comparing the
137 *flo*- mutants with additional camelina accessions, we identified metabolites that could be used as predictive
138 markers of flowering time in seeds and leaves.

139

140 **Results**

141 *Drought impacts strongly the flo- branching phenotype but slightly the flowering precocity*

142

143 We selected six mutants among the previously described camelina *flo*- mutants that show a range of early
144 flowering, determinate growth and branching phenotypes (Bellec et al., 2022; Figure 1, Figure S1A). The *flo*-
145 mutants were subjected to two different drought stresses, before flowering (stress 1) or during flowering at seed
146 set (stress 2). Early drought (stress 1) was used to evaluate the impact of water limitation on flowering time and
147 lateral shoot formation. We monitored the soil water content (SWC) with control plants at 50% SWC and early

148 drought stress was applied on 2 week-old plants (Figure S1B–C). By examining the morphology of the shoot apical
149 meristem, we observed that at this stage none of the meristems of the mutants carried flowers. However, the
150 meristems of the *B1-2* and *C2-19* mutants showed leaf primordia with axillary meristems in their axils, suggesting
151 that they had undergone floral transition (Grbić and Bleecker, 2000; Figure S2). Water loss was conducted until
152 15% SWC for which wilting was observed (40-80% of the plants at day 22, 26 and 29; Figure S1C–D) and these
153 stress conditions were maintained for 10 days. We measured the leaf water content (LWC) before water loss
154 (T_0), during water loss (day 12), at the end of the stress period (day 30) and 4 days after the recovery to 50%
155 SWC (day 34) (Figure S1E). At the end of the stress 1, significant decrease in LWC was observed in all genotypes
156 (Figure S1E). There was no significant difference of LWC between wild type and *flo-* mutants in control conditions,
157 at the end of the drought period (day 30) and during recovery (day 34). However, the *C2-19*, *B23-3* and *A4-12*
158 mutants showed transient tolerance to water loss at day 12, with no significant LWC reduction while Celine and
159 the other *flo-* mutants showed a significant decrease in LWC already (Figure S1E). Together, these data showed
160 a strong impact of the stress on all genotypes tested and suggest that the *C2-19*, *B23-3* and *A4-12* mutants may
161 be more tolerant to mild drought.

162 The *flo-* mutants showed, as expected, early flowering time from 39.5 days for *B1-2* to 49.3 days for *A1-14*
163 compared to wild type Celine (55.6 days) (Figure 1B, Table S1). The observation of the meristem fate in control
164 condition confirmed the early flowering transition in the *flo-* mutants (3 weeks for *A40-24*, *B1-2* and *C2-19*; 4
165 weeks for *A1-14*, *A4-12* and *B23-3*) compared to wild type Celine (5 weeks) (Figure S2). Early drought induced a
166 decrease in flowering time of 3.2 days for wild type plants but impacted differently the *flo-* mutants (Figure 1B).
167 *C2-19*, *A40-24* and *A1-14* mutants showed reduced flowering time upon stress similar to wild type (2.6, 3.3, 3.6
168 days). *B1-2*, *B23-3* and *A4-12* however did not show any significant modification of flowering time in response to
169 early drought stress. Reduction of flowering time was most probably due to a modification of flower emergence
170 and not floral transition since no difference of total leaf number could be observed in all genotypes except for
171 *A1-14*, the less precocious mutant (Figure S3A). Among the *flo-* mutants, *A1-14* and *A4-12* were characterized by
172 their increased number of basal branches compared to wild type (Figure 1A). Branch number was defined at the
173 end of the stress period when wild type camelina still did not have any inflorescence. *B23-3* enhanced branching
174 was caused by an increase in inflorescence branches rather than basal branches (Figure 1A and C and Figure S3B).
175 Interestingly, drought stress strongly reduced the total number of branches (inflorescence and basal) for all *flo-*
176 mutants except for *B1-2* that had the lowest branch number (Figure 1A and Figure S3B). Altogether, our results
177 showed that early drought stress during development strongly impacted the *flo-* branching trait but only mildly
178 flowering time.

179

180 *Early and late drought stresses showed contrasting impact on seed yield in wild type and the flo- mutants*

181

182 Early drought stress induced in wild type a significant reduction of plant height, total seed number and seed yield
183 while increasing thousand seed weight (Figure 2, Figure S4). A similar response for plant height and seed yield
184 could be observed in the *flo-* mutants except for *B1-2*, the shortest genotype (Figure 2A–B). However, except for
185 *A4-12*, thousand seed weight did not increase in *flo-* mutants upon stress and even slightly decreased for *B23-3*

186 (Figure 2C). The contrasting responses on seed traits between wild type and *flo*- mutants could be explained by
187 the fact that the *flo*- mutations already had a strong impact on seed yield, from -80.4% for *B1-2* to -16.9% for *A1-*
188 *14* in control conditions (Figure 2B). To better evaluate the impact of drought stress on seed yield and quality,
189 we carried out a second drought experiment (stress 2) that started when plants had open flowers. For this
190 purpose, the 10-day drought at 15% SWC was carried out on 6 week-old plants for the *flo*- mutants and on 8
191 week-old plants for the Celine wild-type so that drought would be occurring during seed set (Figure S1B, F–G).
192 The transition from 50% SWC to 15% SWC was slower for the *flo*- mutants (12 days) compared to Celine (3 days)
193 (Figure S1B). Wilting was also more severe in stress 2 for both the *flo*- mutants (100% at day 17 and 20) and
194 Celine (100% at day 26 and 31) compared to stress 1, most probably caused by the larger plant size (Figure S1F–
195 G). Stress 2 had a lower impact on wild type plant height compared to stress 1, as it was applied later in
196 development. On the contrary, most *flo*- mutants showed similar plant height in stress 1 and stress 2 experiments
197 except for *B23-3*, the tallest mutant (Figure 2A). Notably, *flo*- mutants and wild type seed yield was significantly
198 reduced by drought, both stress 1 and 2 or exclusively by stress 2, except for *B1-2* that was not impacted by
199 water deficiency (Figure 2B). Stress 2 had less impact on total seed number compared to stress 1 and did not
200 lead to thousand seed weight increase in both wild type and *flo*- mutants (Figure 2C and Figure S4). The *B23-3*
201 mutant even showed a lower thousand seed weight in stress 2 compared to the control (Figure 2C). In conclusion,
202 drought at flowering (stress 2) had a stronger impact on seed yield in the *flo*- mutants than earlier in development
203 (stress 1). Therefore, to investigate seed quality, the analysis was only performed on seeds from stress 2 plants.

204

205 *Lipidomic profile of wild type and flo- seeds after drought stress*

206

207 To understand how drought could impact lipid profile characterized by high polyunsaturated fatty acid content
208 in camelina seeds, we first used a targeted approach to quantify fatty acids in wild type and the *flo*- mutants.
209 While no difference was observed in total fatty content (Figure S5A), principal component analysis (PCA) of the
210 fatty acid composition showed that axis 1 accounting for 39% of the variance, discriminated between the bushy
211 *A1-14* and *A4-12* mutants and the other genotypes (Figure S5B). Notably, these mutants accumulated
212 significantly more saturated fatty acids (C18:0, C20:0 and C22:0) than the wild type in control conditions (Figure
213 S5C, Data S1). However, these differences represented less than 1% of the total fatty acids (Figure S5D). Next,
214 untargeted lipidomic was carried out on control and stressed seeds of wild type and the *flo*- mutants identifying
215 252 lipids with a putative annotation (Data S2). PCA was able to discriminate genotypes in axis 2 accounting for
216 11% of the variance, with three main groups, (i) wild type with *A40-24*, *B1-2* and *C2-19*, (ii) *B23-23*, and finally
217 (iii) *A1-14* with *A4-12* (Figure 3A). ANOVA simultaneous component analysis (ASCA) could not discriminate an
218 effect of the drought stress ($p=0.07$) while the genotypes were more discriminants ($p=0.01$). A total of 79 (30.7%)
219 lipids were differentially accumulated across all conditions (Figure 3B and Table S2). A very minor part of the
220 lipidome, between 1.1% for *C2-19* and 7.1% for *A4-12*, was differentially accumulated upon stress (Figure 3B).
221 Hierarchical clustering of the 79 differentially accumulated metabolites identified two main clusters (cluster 1
222 and 2) that could be separated in six different subclusters defining specific lipid families (Figures 3C–D). Cluster
223 1A represented mostly by sphingolipids showed a higher and constitutive accumulation in *B23-3* mutant

224 compared to the other genotypes. Similarly, the lipids of cluster 1B that included mainly phospholipids and
225 galactolipids were accumulated in *B23-3* and in the branched mutants *A4-12* and *A1-14*. Interestingly, these lipids
226 were also reduced in wild type by the presence of drought (Figure 3D). Phospholipids, mostly represented in
227 cluster 2A, were strongly impacted by the mutations for flowering genes. They were less accumulated in all *flo-*
228 mutants, particularly in *C2-19*, *B23-3*, *A1-14* and *A4-12*, compared to wild-type seeds. Members of the Alkyl
229 Hydroxycinnamates (AHC) family, known to be involved in cuticles and suberin, defined the cluster 2B and also,
230 showed reduced content in *B23-3* and in the bushy mutants *A1-14* and *A4-12* compared to wild type (Figure 3D).
231 Finally, clusters 2C and D containing mostly glycerolipids also discriminated the two bushy mutants (Figure 3C).
232 In conclusion, drought stress led to limited but specific changes in seed lipid content in both wild type and *flo-*
233 mutants. Notably, the *A1-14*, *A4-12* and *B23-3* mutants showed specific lipidomic changes compared to wild-
234 type in both control and drought conditions.

235

236 *flo- seed specialized metabolome is shaped by drought stress*

237

238 Since specialized metabolites are known to be involved in abiotic stress responses (Nakabayashi et al., 2014;
239 Boutet et al., 2022; Barreda et al., 20252024) untargeted metabolomic analysis was also carried out on mature
240 seeds produced in the late drought experiment (stress 2) of wild type and *flo-* mutants. We identified 1761
241 metabolic features accumulated in seeds from wild type camelina and *flo-* mutants among which 1277 (72.5%)
242 were differentially accumulated across genotypes and/or growing conditions (Data S3 and Table S3). The PCA on
243 axis 1 (29% of variance) separated partially the *A1-14* and *A4-12* mutants to the other genotypes. Axis 2
244 discriminated control and stressed samples but in an opposite direction for *flo-* mutants and wild type (Figure
245 4A). Contrary to the lipidomic dataset, the result of the ASCA for specialized metabolome showed a significant
246 effect of both genotypes and drought stress ($p < 0.05$). First, we analyzed the metabolomic response to drought
247 in the different genotypes. In wild type seeds, 202 features were differentially accumulated in response to stress
248 from which only 38 were genotype specific (Figure 4B, blue arrow). Eleven features including putative sinapic
249 acid and two putative flavonoids were specifically modulated in response to drought in all *flo-* mutant seeds
250 while not responding in wild type seeds (Figure 4B, red star; Figure S6). Clustering of the genotypes with the 202
251 wild type differentially accumulated features highlighted three accumulation patterns (Figure S7): mutants that
252 followed the wild type response (*A40-24* and *B1-2*), mutants that showed the wild type stress response in control
253 condition (*A1-14* and *A4-12*) and mutants that showed a control response in stress condition (*C2-19* and *B23-3*).
254 Hierarchical clustering of the features identified two main clusters (Figure 4C). Cluster 1 accounted for 64
255 features accumulated in stressed wild type and *B1-2* and *A40-24* but constitutively accumulated in the bushy
256 mutants *A4-12* and *A1-14* (Figure 4C–D) and characterized by the presence of putative flavonoids (isoquercetrin),
257 a putative cinamate-ester (coumaroyl quinic acid), a phenolic compound (p1121) and four lipids (palmitamide,
258 1-Hexadecanoyl-sn-glycerol, dilinolenin and 9-octadecenamide) (Figure 4E). Cluster 2 could be separated in three
259 different subclusters. Cluster 2A, including 34 features, showed an opposite pattern of cluster 1 with features
260 that were depleted in stressed wild type and with different mutant responses ranging from no response (*C2-19*)
261 to constitutively stressed (*A4-12*) (Figure 4F). This cluster was characterized by glutathione and a putative

262 glucosinolate (Figure 4G). The two remaining clusters 2B and C showed a more complex pattern associated with
263 the individual genotypes (Figure 4C). Altogether, our data showed that the *flo*- mutants have specific
264 metabolomic changes compared to wild type after drought stress including constitutive stress response of the
265 bushy mutants.

266

267 *Metabolomic and lipidomic integration identified limited but specific lipid and secondary metabolite correlations*

268

269 To understand whether the changes in secondary metabolites may be linked to lipid adjustments, we integrated
270 both specialized metabolite and lipid datasets, using sparse partial least square discriminant analysis (sPLS-DA)
271 for two omics integration (Figure S8A, Rohart et al., 2017). Arrow sample plot from the sPLS-DA, showing how
272 each sample project in both, lipid (arrow start) and specialized metabolites (arrow end), indicated low agreement
273 at the sample level observed for both genotypes (Figure 5A) and response to drought (Figure S8B). Putative lipids
274 and specialized metabolites that define each component were represented in the correlation plot (Figure S8C,
275 correlation coefficient>0.55) and clustered in two networks with a limited number of lipid-metabolite
276 correlations (Figure 5B, correlation coefficient>0.55). The first network accounted for lipids and specialized
277 metabolites that explains the separation of the *A1-14* and *A4-12* bushy mutants from the other genotypes,
278 included two putative nitrogen-containing compounds (p771 and p769) and an unknown feature (p772) and
279 seven triglycerides (Figure 5B). The second network, that strongly participated to the separation of component
280 2 (Figure S8A), discriminating partially control and stressed samples, showed negative correlations between the
281 putative HydroxyCinnamic Acid (HCA), sinapoyl-glucose (p74) and siribinose A6 (p178) and the Alkyl
282 HydroxyCinnamates (AHCs), C18:1-coumarate (n15), C18:2-coumarate (230) et C19:1-coumarate (n104) (Figure
283 5B–C). Altogether, these results suggest that lipid remodeling is largely independent from changes in secondary
284 metabolism. However, specific adjustments in the accumulation of alkyl hydroxycinnamates and
285 hydroxycinnamic acids may occur in response to drought.

286

287 *Specialized metabolite landscape of edited flowering mutant seeds and leaves*

288

289 To further explore the impact of early flowering mutations on specialized metabolite profiles, we analyzed the
290 725 seed metabolic features that were differentially accumulated among genotypes in control condition (41% of
291 the total metabolites quantified, Table S4). Enrichment analysis did not allow the identification of profound
292 modification on metabolite family or family group in this list (Figure S9A–B, Table S4). The hierarchical clustering
293 of these features highlighted two groups of genotypes with the bushy mutants *A1-14* and *A4-12* in group 1 and
294 the remaining genotypes in group 2, validating that mutations in different genes affecting both flowering time
295 and shoot architecture revealed a highly specific seed metabolic signature (Figure S10A). The twenty most
296 discriminating features between these two groups were identified by sPLS-DA component 1 (22% of the variance)
297 (Figure 6A and Table S5). Out of the 20 features, three were annotated as putative flavonoids (isorhamnetin 3-
298 rutinoside, isoquercetrin) and lipid (palmitamide) (Figure 6B). Since florigen is synthesized in leaves, we also
299 investigated whether *flo*- mutants have specific specialized metabolic responses in these tissues. A total of 913

300 features were identified, among which 132 (14.5%) were differentially accumulated across genotypes
301 highlighting lower inter-genotype metabolic diversity in leaves compared to seeds (Data S4, Table S4). In this
302 tissue as well, no significant enrichment of metabolic families could be detected (Figure S9C–D, Table S4). Unlike
303 seeds, hierarchical clustering identified three groups with wild type and *A40-24* (group I) having an opposite
304 pattern of accumulation than *A4-12* and *A1-14* (group II). The *B1-2*, *C2-19* and *B23-3* mutants (group III) showed
305 a more complex pattern of accumulation (Figure S10B). The sPLS-DA ran with these groups, showed that
306 component 1 (24% of the variance) was able to discriminate between the wild type and *A40-24* group from the
307 other genotypes (Figure 6C). Component 2 (9% of the variance) discriminated against the bushy mutants from
308 the *B1-2*, *C2-19* and *B23-3* (group III). Out of the twenty most discriminating features of component 1 only ferulic
309 acid could be annotated (Figure 6D and Table S5). In conclusion, the *flo-* mutants showed specific metabolic
310 signatures both in seeds and in leaves with higher metabolite variation among genotypes in seeds compared to
311 leaves. In both tissues, the differences in metabolite profiles mainly reflected the diverse combinations of
312 complex mutations and were not associated with flowering time.

313

314 *Identification of specialized metabolites in seeds and leaves correlated with flowering time*

315

316 To identify metabolite features specifically correlated with flowering time, we explored the metabolome of late-
317 and early-flowering natural accessions of camelina in addition to the *flo-* mutants (Figure S11A–B). The CAM151
318 plants showed similar flowering time than the wild type accession Celine (56.6 days), while CAM203 flowered
319 later at 67.2 days and CAM221, CN101981 and L2F4 flowered earlier like the latest *flo-* mutants (Figure S11B).
320 These accessions did not show strong modifications in shoot architecture (Figure S11A). The seed yield showed
321 the same differences across the genotypes compared to flowering time (Figure S11C). Untargeted lipidomic and
322 metabolomic analyses were carried out in seeds and leaves of these accessions and the PCA analyses showed
323 that the *flo-* mutants were always grouped with wild type compared to the natural accession lines with the
324 exception of L2F4 that clustered with *flo-* mutants for leaf specialized metabolites (Figure 7A–C). These results
325 demonstrate that the *flo-* mutants have a specific metabolome that was closer to the wild type accession Celine,
326 from which they originate, than the other accessions even if they share similar flowering time. By combining all
327 the data together with all the different genotypes, correlation network analysis of metabolic changes confirmed
328 the high correlation between flowering time and yield with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.92 (Figure 7D
329 and F). In seeds, two and six metabolites were respectively positively and negatively correlated with flowering
330 time and only two with yield (Figure 7D). Flowering time was positively correlated with sucrose content while
331 negatively correlated with putative kynurenic acid and putative vitamin B2 (riboflavin) in seeds (Figure 7E).
332 Interestingly, a different network was found in leaves with seven interconnected metabolites that were
333 negatively correlated with flowering time and one negatively correlated with yield from which none were
334 annotated (Figure 7F). These metabolites could be therefore used as predictive markers of flowering time in
335 vegetative tissues.

336

337

338 **Discussion**

339 The use of camelina in summer intercropping or relay cropping could be at risk of adverse growing conditions in
340 particular with drought during vegetative and flowering stages as well as suboptimal conditions during seed
341 maturation. The latter risk could be mitigated by shortening camelina flowering time but not at the expense of
342 drought tolerance. Severe early-stage drought induced a reduction of flowering time in camelina as shown
343 previously for other Brassicaceae such as *Arabidopsis* or *Brassica rapa* with respectively 2–3.8 days and 1.9–8.5
344 days precocity (Franks et al., 2007; Riboni et al., 2013). Similar drought escape strategy was observed in camelina
345 (3.2 days for wild type plants) albeit this crop was naturally tolerant to many abiotic stress (Enjalbert et al., 2013;
346 Gugel and Falk, 2006; Zanetti et al., 2017). In *B. rapa*, plants escape drought by flowering early rather than by
347 increasing water use efficiency and this response could be inherited through natural selection in multiyear
348 drought conditions (Franks, 2011; Franks et al., 2007; Rathnayake and Parachnowitsch, 2025).

349
350 The flowering time observed for all the *flo*- mutants and natural camelina accessions was strongly correlated
351 with reduced seed yield in both control and drought conditions. This negative correlation between flowering
352 time and seed yield was also observed in *Arabidopsis* (Gnan et al., 2014). Branching was also associated with
353 seed yield reduction in two out of the seven *flo*- mutants as observed in *Arabidopsis* or during maize
354 domestication (Doebley et al., 1997; Gnan et al., 2014). Notably, an increase in thousand seed weight in response
355 to drought applied at an early developmental stage was observed, as previously been reported in camelina
356 (Alberghini et al., 2025). Increased thousand-seed weight was also detected in some *flo*- mutants under control
357 conditions, consistent with the larger seed size previously described in some of them (Bellec et al., 2022). As the
358 total number of seeds produced was drastically reduced in both the *flo*- mutants and the wild type under early
359 drought stress, the increase in thousand seed weight may reflect a compensatory mechanism leading to a higher
360 assimilate allocation per seed. While seed yield is a secondary trait for cover cropping strategy, the ability to
361 grow camelina in intercropping conditions would very much rely on its ability to be competitive against weeds
362 (Leclère et al., 2018). In the *flo*- bushy mutants *A4-12* and *A1-14*, the branching phenotype was completely
363 abolished upon drought stress, potentially limiting the use of this trait in the field. Nonetheless, in all mutants,
364 flowering precocity was not associated with enhanced sensitivity to severe drought conditions (15% SWC). In
365 intermediate drought conditions (25% SWC, during water lose), Leaf Water Content (LWC) was not changed
366 compared to control conditions in three mutants (*C2-19*, *B23-3*, *A4-12*) contrary to wild type suggesting a
367 potential tolerance of these genotypes to milder drought. Altogether, our results indicate that the *flo*- mutants
368 are good candidates for relay cropping during summer as they most certainly be able to complete their life cycle
369 before autumn in field condition. However, the loss of the bushy phenotype upon drought could limit its ability
370 to control weed development.

371
372 The great potential of camelina in intercropping relies not only on its cover crop ability but also on its oil and co-
373 product production (Zanetti et al., 2021). It was therefore important to assess the effect of drought and precocity
374 on seed lipid profile as well as specialized metabolites in both seeds and leaves. The environmental effect on

375 fatty acid profile in camelina were reported as important (Brock et al., 2020; Raziei et al., 2018; Vollmann et al.,
376 2007) or moderate to low (Boutet *et al.*, 2022) most likely depending of the field conditions and the nature of
377 abiotic and abiotic stress occurring during the trials. Here we showed that drought stress did not have an
378 important effect on seed lipid fatty acids even in *flo*- mutants indicating that flowering precocity like water
379 restriction were not impacting oil quality in camelina. Nonetheless, the *flo*- mutants showed specific changes in
380 some lipid families like phospholipids in particular polyunsaturated medium chain phosphatidylcholine (PC38.5,
381 PC38.4, PC36.6 PC34.4, PC34.6). Remodeling of cell membranes are often observed in response to abiotic
382 stresses such as drought in particular for thylakoid membranes allowing a structural re-shaping and maintenance
383 of chloroplasts function and photosynthetic energy supply both in leaves like in seeds (Gasulla et al., 2013;
384 Torres-Franklin et al., 2007 Ferreira et al., 2021). Notably, the ratio between polyunsaturated and saturated fatty
385 acids is enhanced to improve membrane fluidity protecting cells from damage (Gigon et al., 2004; Upchurch,
386 2008).

387
388 By contrast, specialized metabolites were strongly affected by drought stress in the different genotypes (72.5%
389 of quantified metabolites) with specific responses, confirming previous work in field experiment (Boutet *et al.*,
390 2022). The *flo*- mutants showed differential stress response for their seed specialized metabolites. The bushy
391 mutants *A1-14* and *A4-12* constitutively accumulated stressed wild type metabolic profile while *C2-19* and *B23-3*
392 mutants did not show any wild type stress response. The last two mutants, *A40-24* and to lesser extent *B1-2*,
393 were having the same specialized metabolic signature as wild type. The constitutive drought signature observed
394 in the seeds of the *A1-14* and *A4-12* mutants is most likely not associated with their flowering precocity, as
395 drought appeared to have only a minor effect on flowering time, and the *flo*- mutants showing the greatest
396 precocity did not display a constitutive drought signature. This constitutive stress signature may result from
397 reduced carbon allocation to seeds, likely due to the high number of lateral shoots in these plants, a phenomenon
398 also described in other Brassicaceae species (Bennett et al., 2012; Van Daele et al., 2012).

399
400 Specialized metabolite signature of the drought response in wild type seeds included glutathione, the flavonoid
401 isoquercetrin, the cinnamate ester coumaroyl quinic acid and modified lipids like dilinolenin, 1-hexadecanoyl-sn-
402 glycerol and 9-octadecenamide. Notably, several of these metabolites are strong antioxidants known to be
403 involved in abiotic stresses (Rai et al., 2023; Soviguidi et al., 2022). In particular, glutathione was accumulated
404 upon drought in seeds in wild type but constitutively accumulated in the *A1-14* and *A4-12* *flo*- mutants.
405 Glutathione has been involved in drought tolerance in *Arabidopsis* in particular by inducing translational changes
406 in hormonal and stress-signaling pathway (Cheng et al., 2015). Eleven metabolites, including sinapic acid, were
407 specifically accumulated upon drought in seeds in *flo*- mutant while not modulated by stress in the wild type.
408 Many abundant cinnamic acids in Brassicaceae seeds derive from sinapic acid core structure and decorated
409 metabolites, mainly sinapate esters (COO-R) (Baumert et al., 2005; Boutet et al., 2022; Corso et al., 2020). Sinapic
410 acid and sinapate esters were involved in a wide range of stress responses in Brassicaceae species, including
411 reduction of oxidative stress damage and UV-stress (Milkowski and Strack, 2010). In addition, cinnamic acids,
412 including sinapic acid and some derivatives, showed a strong antioxidant and antibacterial activity against plant

413 and human pathogens (Engels et al., 2012; König et al., 2014; tesaki et al., 1998). Glutathione and sinapic acid or
414 its derivatives were described to interfere with abscisic acid (Bi et al., 2017; Cheng et al., 2015). It is also well
415 described that abscisic acid is involved in shoot branching, presenting a putative explanation for the differences
416 in these metabolite levels in the bushy mutants *A1-14* and *A4-12* (Yao and Finlayson, 2015).

417

418 In leaves, ferulic acid was lower in all *flo-* mutants but *A40-24* compared to wild type. Ferulic acid is one of the
419 most abundant HydroxyCinnamic Acid (HCA) in plants and its accumulation is correlated with drought resistance
420 in wheat and barley (Hura et al., 2009; Piasecka et al., 2017). The HCA are metabolites involved in cell wall
421 structures by covalently binding to hemicellulose arabinoxylans improving plant rigidification and limiting water
422 loss (Zeiss et al., 2021). We also observed specific changes in other HCA derivatives Alkyl HydroxyCinnamates
423 (AHC), C18-ferulate, C16-coumarate, C15-coumarate, C17-ferulate in particular in the *A1-14* and *A4-12* bushy
424 mutants. In camelina, AHC were previously characterized as predominantly alkyl coumarates and alkyl caffeates
425 (Razeq et al., 2014). The AHC are present in suberin-associated waxes and cuticular waxes that are important
426 components for preventing water loss (Delude et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2014). Seeds AHCs were reduced in the
427 branched *flo-* mutants and could therefore impact seed quality (Vishwanath et al., 2013). The adjustment
428 between specific HCA and AHC was also pointed out in the metabolome and lipidome integration analysis,
429 indicating potential cross-regulation between these lipids and the phenylpropanoid pathway in response to
430 drought. Overall, the integration of lipidomic and metabolomic data suggests that lipid remodeling is largely
431 independent of changes in secondary metabolism. This result was expected, since drought exerted a stronger
432 influence on the modulation of specialized metabolites than on lipid composition in seeds.

433

434 Finally, including additional genotypes with distinct flowering time but without major change in shoot
435 architecture, we identified metabolites strongly correlating with this trait. As expected, sucrose was correlated
436 with flowering time as observed in many species (Cho et al. 2018). But except for hormone metabolism and
437 carbohydrate availability, there is limited information regarding the specialized metabolic changes that take
438 place at floral transition (Wahl et al., 2013, Izawa, 2021; Praena Tamayo et al., 2022). Our results indicate a
439 correlation between flowering time and several putative specialized metabolites including vitamin B2 and
440 kynurenic acid, a tryptophan catabolite in seeds.

441

442 In conclusion, the early flowering phenotype observed in the edited camelina lines did not modify their tolerance
443 to drought but revealed specific changes in specialized metabolites. These changes were however far less
444 extended than those observed in camelina natural diversity (Figure 7). The camelina *flo-* mutants represent
445 nonetheless valuable genetic resources for summer intercropping and their potential use would still need to be
446 validated in open field trials.

447

448 **Materials and Methods**

449 *Plant material and growth conditions*

450 The experiments were performed using camelina (*Camelina sativa*) cultivars Celine, CAM221, CAM151, CAM203,
451 from the BAZ, Braunschweig Genetic Resources Centre, CN101981 from Canadian Plant Gene Resources of
452 Canada (GRIN-Global-CA), the recombinant line L2F4 from the INRAE breeding program GENESYS PIVERT
453 Probioraff and the *C2-19*, *B1-2*, *B23-3*, *A40-24* *A4-12* and *A1-14* mutants described in Bellec et al., (2022). These
454 mutants are in the Celine genetic background and we name them “*flo*- mutants” because of their different
455 combinations of mutations in flowering time genes *CsFLC*, *CsSVP*, *CsLHP1*, *CsTFL1* and *CsELF3* (Bellec et al., 2022,
456 Figure S1A). Seeds were germinated first on paper disk in Petri dishes for 4 days before transferring the seedlings
457 to soil in a long day (LD, 16 h light: 8 h dark) glasshouse supplemented with artificial light when necessary, with
458 24 °C day and 13 °C night temperatures. For the drought experiments, soil water content (SWC) was estimated
459 using pot weight. For this purpose, all 14-cm \varnothing pots of both early (stress 1) and late (stress 2) drought experiment
460 were filled with 800 g of soil. Ten pots were used as control pots to calculate pot weight at 100% SWC and 0%
461 SWC as follows. Pots were first soaked into water and we let the water run out of the pot by gravity for 1-hour
462 to estimate pot weight at field capacity (100% SWC). The same pots were subsequently dried using a dry oven to
463 estimate their weight at 0% SWC. The percentage of SWC across the experiment was calculated subsequently: %
464 SWC = ((pot weight - weight at 0% SWC) / weight at 100% SWC) x 100. The pot weight was corrected in the
465 experiment to account for plant weight. For this purpose, shoots of control plants were harvested and weighted
466 at 5 weeks (3g), 6 weeks (7g) and 8 weeks (25g). For early drought experiment (stress 1), seedlings were first
467 watered 12 days until all pots reached 50% SWC, then control plants were kept at a 50% SWC while stress plants
468 were water deprived until 15% SWC and maintained at 15% SWC for 10 days before recovering 50% SWC for 3
469 days (Figure S1B–C). Later, plants were watered without monitoring the % SWC. The late drought experiment
470 (stress 2) was carried out at flowering (Figure S1B). For this purpose, the 10-day drought at 15% SWC was carried
471 out on 6 week-old plants for the *flo*- mutants and on 8 week-old plants for the Celine wild-type (Figure S1B and
472 F). In this drought experiment, recovery was not monitored and the three last days of the Celine control had SWC
473 ranging from 73% to 93% while it was maintained at 50% for the *flo*- control. Control plants were the same in
474 both drought experiments (stress 1 and stress 2). Cultivars CAM221, CAM151, CAM203, CN101981 and L2F4
475 were cultivated in the same control condition at the same time.

476 *Plant phenotyping*

477 Wilting was monitored using visual observation of the plant. Plant was considered wilted if at least one leaf was
478 wilted. The percentage of whole-leaf water content (%LWC) was calculated as follow: %LWC = ((leaf fresh weight
479 – leaf dry weight) / leaf fresh weight) x 100. Day to flowering was scored at the first flower opening. The branch
480 number and length were carried out at the end of the stress 1, on 6 week-old plants. Final plant height was
481 measured when plants were completely dried. Thousand seed weight was counted using an elmor C3 seed
482 counter. At least 10–12 plants were used for each condition.

483 *Confocal laser scanning microscopy*

484 Shoot apices of Celine and *flo*- mutants were dissected under a stereomicroscope at 2, 3, 4 and 5 weeks after
485 sowing and fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA). The samples were vacuum-infiltrated twice for 10 min each
486 and transferred to fresh PFA at 4°C overnight before clearing with ClearSee (Kurihara et al., 2015) for 3 to 7 days.
487 Cell wall was dyed using 0.1% (v/v) SCRI Renaissance 2200 (Musielak et al., 2015) one day before imaging and
488 imaged with an SP8 (Leica Microsystems) using excitation wavelength: 405 nm; detection wavelength: 410–510
489 nm. At least 3–6 plants were observed under the stereomicroscope for this experiment.

490 *Extraction, quantification and annotation of lipid and specialized metabolites fractions*

491 Mature dry seeds and leaves from vegetative plants of Celine, CAM221, CAM151, CAM203, CN101981, L2F4 and
492 the *flo*- mutants in control condition and mature dry seeds of Celine and the *flo*- mutants under drought stress
493 were used in this experiment. For this purpose, flowers were marked individually on the first day of opening on
494 the starting day of the drought period (stress 2) and on the same day in the control plants (Figure S1F). Mature
495 dry seeds from three marked siliques of three plants were pooled and grinded using a HG-600 Geno/Grinder®
496 2010. Leaves number four were harvested in vegetative plants at four weeks after sowing. Leaves from three
497 plants were pooled for each replicate, dry freeze in liquid nitrogen and ground using SK350 paint shaker.
498 Metabolites were extracted from 30 mg of mature dry seeds or 200 mg of leaves using MeOH:Methyl-tert-
499 butyl:H₂O (1:3:1) for extraction and MeOH:water (1:3) for phase separation, providing an upper organic phase
500 (used for lipid quantification) and a lower aqueous phase (used for polar and semi-polar metabolites
501 quantification) as described in Boutet et al. (2022). Phases were separated and dried down in a SpeedVac vacuum
502 concentrator (Thermo RVT4104). Polar and semi-polar metabolite samples, later called specialized metabolites,
503 were resuspended in 250 µl of acetonitrile:water (1:9) containing 500 ng of Apigenin (used as internal standard)
504 and lipid samples were resuspended in 500 µl of acetonitrile:isopropanol (7:3) (without internal standard). The
505 parameters for liquid chromatography, mass spectrometry, and data treatment used in the untargeted lipidomic
506 and specialized metabolites analysis are described in Boutet et al. (2022), except for the parameters modified as
507 followed. For specialized metabolites, MZmine was run independently for leave and seed samples (Schmid et al.,
508 2023). For lipids and specialized metabolites in leaf samples, molecular networks were generated using cosine
509 score thresholds of 0.65 and 0.7 in negative and positive data, respectively. For specialized metabolites in seed
510 samples, molecular networks were generated using cosine score thresholds of 0.65 and 0.75 in negative and
511 positive data, respectively. Lipid and specialized metabolites annotation were performed in consecutive steps.
512 First, the ESI- and ESI+ lipidomic data used for the molecular networks were searched against our library and the
513 available MS₂ spectral libraries (MassBank.NA, GNPS Public Spectral Library, NIST14 Tandem, and NIH Natural
514 Products), with an absolute m/z tolerance of 0.02, a minimum of 4 matched peaks, and a minimal cosine score
515 of 0.65. For the lipid analysis, the results of the database search were validated in the different clusters of the
516 molecular network using the specific fragments and neutral losses for the different lipid classes and their MS₂
517 spectra (Lipid Class Specific Fragments, Lipidomics Standards Initiative (LSI)). If the database search result was
518 valid, the annotation of other features was performed by stepwise comparison from the valid lipid metabolite.
519 Finally, Sirius software (<https://bio.informatik.uni-jena.de/software/sirius/>) using the CANOPUS algorithm (Kim
520 et al., 2021) was used (Dührkop et al., 2019), in the lipid analysis for clusters of the molecular network with no

521 database search results and in specialized metabolites for all features. For specialized metabolites only, the
522 annotations were further refined to improve unclear ones, with MS2query (de Jonge et al., 2023). A minimum
523 Tanimoto score of 0.65 was set as the threshold for accurate identification. For each feature, a confidence level
524 score ranging from 1 to 4 were assigned as followed: 1 represents exact matches with authentic standards, 2
525 denotes putatively annotated compounds verified through multiple sources, 3 corresponds to compounds
526 identified as part of putative classes, and 4 indicates uncharacterized MS/MS signals (See Data S3 and Data S4;
527 Reisdorff et al., 2020). Lipids that showed the same annotation in positive and negative were manually removed
528 as followed. For TAG, the accumulations in the positive file were selected. For phospholipids found in positive
529 and negative modes, the most sensitive accumulations were selected. However, for phospholipids found in
530 positive and negative modes, annotations containing the fatty acid composition in the negative file were used.
531 For other lipids, the accumulations with the highest value were selected. Accumulations of lipid features were
532 normalized according to the weight of the seeds used for extraction. Accumulations of specialized metabolite
533 features were normalized according to the weight of the seeds and/or leaves used for extraction and the internal
534 standard Apigenin.

535 *Extraction and quantification of the fatty acids*

536 Twenty mg of the same mature dry seed samples of Celine and the *flo*- mutants in control condition and under
537 drought stress used for polar/semipolar specialized metabolites and lipid extraction was used for fatty acid
538 quantification. Total fatty acids were measured after fatty acids methyl ester (FAME) preparation from 2 mg of
539 material followed by gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis as previously
540 described (Li et al., 2006).

541 *Statistical analysis*

542 Phenotyping data were analyzed using two factor analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by a Tukey post hoc test
543 for pairwise multiple comparisons using R (<http://r-project.org/>). Complete statistical results are presented in
544 Table S1. For graphical representation, only significant differences between conditions (control, stress 1 and
545 stress 2) were presented for each genotype. For statistical analysis of the specialized metabolites, only the
546 metabolite with variation coefficient CQ > 20% were used. Metabolite data were first normalized by the median,
547 Log transformed (base 10) and scaled by mean-centered and divided by the standard deviation of each variable
548 using MetaboAnalyst 5.0 (<https://www.metaboanalyst.ca/>) (Pang et al., 2022). Principal component analysis
549 (PCA), sparse partial least square discriminant analysis (sPLS-DA) and loadings plot presenting the discriminant
550 features were performed using the mixOmics package in R (Rohart et al., 2017). We used the ANOVA-
551 simultaneous component analysis (ASCA) model in MetaboAnalyst with 100 permutations to determine the
552 impact of each factor (genotypes and conditions) and their interaction. Visual observation of the PCA and results
553 of the ASCA that showed no significance of the interaction between both factors (specialized metabolite
554 pvalue=0.22, lipids pvalue=0.1) lead us to compare the samples independently using the ANOVA followed by a
555 Fisher's LSD post hoc analysis (FDR *p-value* < 0.05) in MetaboAnalyst. Upset plots were produced using the

556 UpSetR package (Conway et al., 2017). Hierarchical dendrograms using Ward algorithm and heat map were made
557 in MetaboAnalyst. The cluster separations were identified using hierarchical clustering dendrograms and based
558 on visual assessment. The integration of lipidome and specialized metabolome datasets, to explore potential
559 associations between lipid features and specialized metabolite features, was performed using a covariance-
560 based multiscale integration approach, operated with the sPLS-DA for two omics integration function in the
561 mixOmics package in R (Rohart et al., 2017). From the sPLS-DA, arrow sample plots, correlation circle plot and
562 relevance network were generated using mixOmics. For the correlation circle plot and the network analysis
563 representations, only associations with correlation coefficient > 0.55, considered moderate to strong associations
564 (Schober and Schwarte, 2018), were used. Networks were represented using Cytoscape focusing only on lipids-
565 metabolite correlations (Shannon et al., 2003). The enrichment analysis of the different metabolite families
566 within significantly regulated features in control leaves and seeds were carried as in Boutet et al. (2022) and
567 correlation analysis between flowering time, seed yield and the specialized metabolites were performed using
568 Cytoscape (Shannon et al., 2003).

569 **Data Availability**

570 The lipidomic (LC-MS/MS) data on camelina seeds have been deposited at the MassIVE data repository portal
571 with the identifier MSV000098002 (doi:10.25345/C5BZ61M9C). The untargeted metabolomic (LC-MS/MS) data
572 on camelina seeds and leaves have been deposited at the MassIVE data repository portal with the identifier
573 MSV000098012 (doi:10.25345/C52J68H4W).

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583 **Author Contributions**

584 JDF and AV conceptualized the research. AV, MW and MV grew the plants, conducted the drought experiment,
585 the phenotyping and sample collections. AV and LB extracted the samples for LC-MS/MS. SB and JCT generated
586 the LC-MS/MS data, performed the metabolite quantification and annotation. ADC extracted the fatty acid. FT
587 carried out the fatty acid quantification and annotation. AV and MC performed the statistical analyses. AV, JDF

588 and MC interpreted the data. AV and JDF wrote the original draft with contribution from MC. All authors
589 commented on and approved the submitted version.

590 **Disclosures**

591 Conflicts of interest: No conflicts of interest declared

592

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785

786 **Figure legends:**

787

788 **Figure 1:** Drought impacts strongly the *flo*- branching phenotype but slightly the flowering precocity

789 A, Picture of the wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14* mutants in the control condition (top)
790 and 4 days after the end of the 10-day drought stress (bottom; day 34). Arrows indicate the absence of lateral
791 branches in the *A1-14* and *A4-12* mutants. Bar, 15-cm. B, Days to flowering (days to the first flower open) of the
792 wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14* mutants in the control and in response to drought (stress
793 1). C, Branch number of the wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14* mutants observed at the
794 end of the 10-day drought stress (day 30) in the control and in response to drought (stress 1). In B and C, boxes
795 indicate the interquartile range, the vertical line in the middle is the median, the horizontal lines (whiskers)

796 correspond to the highest or lowest value within 1.5 times the interquartile range, letters show significant
797 differences between conditions and genotypes ($p < 0.05$, using ANOVA followed by Tukey's pairwise multiple
798 comparisons), $n = 10$ to 12

799

800 **Figure 2:** Drought before and after flowering impacts final plant size and yield

801 A-C, Final plant length (A), seed yield (B) and thousand seeds weight (C) of wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*,
802 *A4-12* and *A1-14* plants in control condition and in response to early drought (stress 1) and drought at
803 flowering (stress 2). Boxes indicate the interquartile range, the vertical line in the middle is the median, the
804 horizontal lines (whiskers) correspond to the highest or lowest value within 1.5 times the interquartile range,
805 letters show significant differences between conditions only ($p < 0.05$, using ANOVA followed by Tukey's pairwise
806 multiple comparisons; additional pairwise comparisons between genotypes are available in Table S1), $n = 10$ to
807 12.

808

809 **Figure 3:** Seed lipidome showed only few metabolic changes after drought stress in wild type camelina

810 A, Principal component analysis (PCA) showing the positions of samples in the plane delineated by component 1
811 and 2 accounting for 43% of the total variance between the 178 features identified as accumulated in mature
812 seeds of the wt and the *flo-* mutants (*A1-14*, *A4-12*, *A40-24*, *B1-2*, *B23-3* and *C2-19*) in control condition (triangles)
813 and in response to stress 2 (circles). B, UpSet plot showing the number of features differentially accumulated in
814 the control condition compared to stress 2 (P -values after ANOVA and Fisher's FDR correction lower than 0.05)
815 for each of the genotype, wt and the *flo-* mutants (bottom left hand side) and the number of unique and shared
816 differentially accumulated features (right-hand side). This UpSet plot represents 61% of the total differential
817 features. The grey box shows the intersections that account for 50% of the 79 significantly regulated features
818 across genotypes and conditions. The plot on the right-hand side shows the number of features with differential
819 accumulation under drought specific to a single genotype (indicated by a black circle alone) and those with shared
820 differential accumulation across genotypes (indicated by black circles connected by a line). For example, the most
821 frequent combination corresponded to features differentially accumulated upon drought only in the wt, followed
822 by features showing shared differential accumulation under stress in *B23-3* and *A4-12*. C, Heat map representing
823 the hierarchical clustering of the 79 features significantly regulated features in at least one of the pairwise
824 comparison. Stars shows significant difference between wt control vs wt stress 2 with P -values after ANOVA and
825 Fisher's FDR correction lower than 0.05. D, Box plots of the normalized accumulation profile of features of cluster
826 1A, 1B, 2A and 2B. In B and C the black stars indicate the 16 features significantly regulated in the wt in response
827 to stress 2, the red star the features highly accumulated in response to stress 2 in all *flo-* mutant but not in the
828 wt.

829

830 **Figure 4:** The *flo-* mutants showed a different specialized metabolome response to drought stress in mature
831 seeds compared to the wt

832 A, Principal component analysis (PCA) showing the positions of samples in the plane delineated by component 1
833 and 2 accounting for 41% of the total variance between the 1761 features identified accumulated in mature

834 seeds of the wt and the *flo*- mutants (*A1-14*, *A4-14*, *A40-24*, *B1-2*, *B23-3* and *C2-19*) in control condition (triangles)
 835 and in response to stress 2 (circles). B, UpSet plot showing the number of features differentially accumulated in
 836 the control condition compared to stress 2 (*P-values* after ANOVA and Fisher's FDR correction lower than 0.05)
 837 for each of the genotype, wt and the *flo*- mutants (bottom left hand side) and the number of unique and shared
 838 differentially accumulated features (right-hand side). This UpSet plot represents 59% of the total differential
 839 features. The grey box shows the intersections that account for 50% of the 1277 significantly regulated features
 840 across genotypes and conditions. The plot on the right-hand side shows the number of features with differential
 841 accumulation under drought specific to a single genotype (indicated by a black circle alone) and those with shared
 842 differential accumulation across genotypes (indicated by black circles connected by a line). For example, eleven
 843 features were identified as differentially accumulated under drought in all *flo*- mutants, but not in the wt. C,
 844 Heatmap representing the hierarchical clustering of the 202 features significantly regulated in mature seeds of
 845 the wt in response to stress 2 in all genotypes (wt, *A1-14*, *A4-14*, *A40-24*, *B1-2*, *B23-3* and *C2-19*). Coexpressed
 846 clusters were assigned into two higher level clusters (1 and 2). D and F, box plot of the normalized accumulation
 847 profile of features of cluster 1 (D) and cluster 2A (F). E and G, Structure of the annotated features of cluster 1 (E)
 848 and cluster 2A (G).

849

850 **Figure 5:** Integration of specialized metabolite and lipid features identified correlations between
 851 hydroxycinnamic acids and alkyl hydroxycinnamates

852 A, Arrow sample plot, from the sPLS-DA applied to the lipid and specialized metabolite datasets showing how
 853 each sample project in both. The start and the end of the arrow indicates the sample projection on the two
 854 components from the lipids to the specialized metabolites data respectively. While strong differences between
 855 genotypes in both datasets is observed in dimension 1, the long arrows in all genotypes indicate low agreement
 856 at the sample level. B, Network analysis applied to the lipid and specialized metabolite datasets. Each edge links
 857 a specialized metabolite (square) to a lipid (circle). Only variables selected in the sPLS-DA on the first two
 858 components are represented and filtered with a cutoff of 0.55. Only clusters with pairs of variables belonging to
 859 different omics are presented. Red: positive correlations, blue: negative correlations. C-D, Structures of the
 860 annotated lipid features (C) and specialized metabolites (D) of the network presented on the right in B. In C, the
 861 location of double bonds in the lipid structures are putatives.

862

863 **Figure 6:** The *A4-12* and *A1-14 flo*- mutants show strong modifications of specialized metabolomes in seeds and
 864 leaves

865 A, sPLS-DA showing model discrimination between seed samples of the wt and the *A1-14*, *A4-14*, *A40-24*, *B1-2*,
 866 *B23-3* and *C2-19 flo*- mutants. sPLS-DA allows the selection of the most predictive or discriminative features
 867 within the dataset to classify samples. B, Molecule structures of the annotated putative metabolites in the 20
 868 most discriminating features of component 1 of A. C, sPLS-DA showing model discrimination between leaf
 869 samples of the wt and the *A1-14*, *A4-14*, *A40-24*, *B1-2*, *B23-3* and *C2-19 flo*- mutants. D, Molecule structures of
 870 the annotated putative metabolites in the 20 most discriminating features of component 1 of C. The start

871 indicates that palmitamide (p139) was also identified differentially accumulated in response to drought in the wt
872 (Figure 4E).

873

874 **Figure 7:** Specialized metabolites correlated with flowering time and yield

875 A-C, Principal component analysis (PCA) showing the positions of lipids (A) and specialized metabolites (B and C)
876 samples in the plane delineated by component 1 and 2 in mature seeds (A and B) and in leaves (C) of the wt
877 (Celine), the *flo*- mutants (*B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14*), and the CAM221, L2F4, CN101981,
878 CAM151 and CAM203 additional genotypes. $n = 3$. D and F, Correlation networks of specialized metabolites in
879 mature seeds (D) and leaves (F), FT: Flowering Time, Y: seed Yield, red line: positive correlation > 0.8 , blue line:
880 negative correlation < -0.8 . E, Molecule structures of the annotated putative metabolites in D.

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Figure 1: Drought impacts strongly the *fla*- branching phenotype but slightly the flowering precocity. A, Picture of the wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14* mutants in the control condition (top) and 4 days after the end of the 10-day drought stress (bottom; day 34). Arrows indicate the absence of lateral branches in the *A1-14* and *A4-12* mutants. Bar, 15-cm. B, Days to flowering (days to the first flower open) of the wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14* mutants in the control and in response to drought (stress 1). C, Branch number of the wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14* mutants observed at the end of the 10-day drought stress (day 30) in the control and in response to drought (stress 1). In B and C, boxes indicate the interquartile range, the vertical line in the middle is the median, the horizontal lines (whiskers) correspond to the highest or lowest value within 1.5 times the interquartile range, letters show significant differences between conditions and genotypes ($p < 0.05$, using ANOVA followed by Tukey's pairwise multiple comparisons), $n = 10$ to 12

188x100mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 2: Drought before and after flowering impacts final plant size and yield. A-C, Final plant length (A), seed yield (B) and thousand seeds weight (C) of wt and the B1-2, C2-19, A40-24, B23-3, A4-12 and A1-14 plants in control condition and in response to early drought (stress 1) and drought at flowering (stress 2).

Boxes indicate the interquartile range, the vertical line in the middle is the median, the horizontal lines (whiskers) correspond to the highest or lowest value within 1.5 times the interquartile range, letters show significant differences between conditions only ($p < 0.05$, using ANOVA followed by Tukey's pairwise multiple comparisons; additional pairwise comparisons between genotypes are available in Table S1), $n = 10$ to 12.

2A and 2B. In B and C the black stars indicate the 16 features significantly regulated in the wt in response to stress 2, the red star the features highly accumulated in response to stress 2 in all flo- mutant but not in the wt.

187x203mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 4: The *flo*- mutants showed a different specialized metabolome response to drought stress in mature seeds compared to the wt. **A**, Principal component analysis (PCA) showing the positions of samples in the plane delineated by component 1 and 2 accounting for 41% of the total variance between the 1761 features identified accumulated in mature seeds of the wt and the *flo*- mutants A1-14, A4-12, A40-24, B1-2, B23-3 and C2-19) in control condition (triangles) and in response to stress 2 (circles). **B**, UpSet plot showing the number of features differentially accumulated in the control condition compared to stress 2 (*P*-values after ANOVA and Fisher's FDR correction lower than 0.05) for each of the genotype, wt and the *flo*- mutants (bottom left hand side) and the number of unique and shared differentially accumulated features (right-hand side). This UpSet plot represents 59% of the total differential features. The grey box shows the intersections that account for 50% of the 1277 significantly regulated features across genotypes and conditions. The plot on the right-hand side shows the number of features with differential accumulation under drought specific to a single genotype (indicated by a black circle alone) and those with shared differential accumulation across genotypes (indicated by black circles connected by a line). For example, eleven features were identified as differentially accumulated under drought in all *flo*- mutants, but not in the wt. **C**, Heatmap representing the

hierarchical clustering of the 202 features significantly regulated in mature seeds of the wt in response to stress 2 in all genotypes (wt, *A1-14*, *A4-12*, *A40-24*, *B1-2*, *B23-3* and *C2-19*). Coexpressed clusters were assigned into two higher level clusters (1 and 2). D and F, box plot of the normalized accumulation profile of features of cluster 1 (D) and cluster 2A (F). E and G, Structure of the annotated features of cluster 1 (E) and cluster 2A (G).

181x221mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 5: Integration of specialized metabolite and lipid features identified correlations between hydroxycinnamic acids and alkyl hydroxycinnamates

A, Arrow sample plot, from the sPLS-DA applied to the lipid and specialized metabolite datasets showing how each sample project in both. The start and the end of the arrow indicates the sample projection on the two components from the lipids to the specialized metabolites data respectively. While strong differences between genotypes in both datasets is observed in dimension 1, the long arrows in all genotypes indicate low agreement at the sample level. **B**, Network analysis applied to the lipid and specialized metabolite datasets. Each edge links a specialized metabolite (square) to a lipid (circle). Only variables selected in the sPLS-DA on the first two components are represented and filtered with a cutoff of 0.55. Only clusters with pairs of variables belonging to different omics are presented. Red: positive correlations, blue: negative correlations. **C-D**, Structures of the annotated lipid features (**C**) and specialized metabolites (**D**) of the network presented on the right in **B**. In **C**, the location of double bonds in the lipid structures are putatives.

172x102mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 6: The *A4-12* and *A1-14 flo-* mutants show strong modifications of specialized metabolomes in seeds and leaves A, sPLS-DA showing model discrimination between seed samples of the wt and the *A1-14*, *A4-14*, *A40-24*, *B1-2*, *B23-3* and *C2-19 flo-* mutants. sPLS-DA allows the selection of the most predictive or discriminative features within the dataset to classify samples. B, Molecule structures of the annotated putative metabolites in the 20 most discriminating features of component 1 of A. C, sPLS-DA showing model discrimination between leaf samples of the wt and the *A1-14*, *A4-14*, *A40-24*, *B1-2*, *B23-3* and *C2-19 flo-* mutants. D, Molecule structures of the annotated putative metabolites in the 20 most discriminating features of component 1 of C. The star indicates that palmitamide (p139) was also identified differentially accumulated in response to drought in the wt (Figure 4E).

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Figure 7: Specialized metabolites correlated with flowering time and yield. A-C, Principal component analysis (PCA) showing the positions of lipids (A) and specialized metabolites (B and C) samples in the plane delineated by component 1 and 2 in mature seeds (A and B) and in leaves (C) of the wt (Celine), the *flo*-mutants (B1-2, C2-19, A40-24, B23-3, A4-12 and A1-14), and the CAM221, L2F4, CN101981, CAM151 and CAM203 additional genotypes. $n = 3$. D and F, Correlation networks of specialized metabolites in mature seeds (D) and leaves (F). FT: Flowering Time, Y: seed Yield, red line: positive correlation > 0.8, blue line: negative correlation < -0.8. E, Molecule structures of the annotated putative metabolites in D.

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	SVP			FLC			Plant & Cell Physiology			TFL1			ELF3		
	SG-1 <i>Csa16g</i> 044290	SG-2 <i>Csa07g</i> 052630	SG-3 <i>Csa09g</i> 086860	SG-1 <i>Csa13g</i> 011890	SG-2 <i>Csa08g</i> 054450	SG-3 <i>Csa20g</i> 015400	SG-1 <i>Csa13g</i> 020480	SG-2 <i>Csa08g</i> 009910	SG-3 <i>Csa20g</i> 025860	SG-1 <i>Csa13g</i> 003940	SG-2 <i>Csa08g</i> 060650	SG-3 <i>Csa20g0</i> 05030	SG-1 <i>Csa16g</i> 047550	SG-2 <i>Csa07g</i> g0569 50	SG-3 <i>Csa09g</i> 092140
A40-24	WT WT	WT WT	WT +C	WT WT	WT +T	WT WT	-20 WT	WT WT	WT WT	+T +A	WT WT	+G WT	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT
A4-12	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT	+C -ACG	WT -4	WT WT	+T WT/-2	WT +A	WT -4 & 2snp	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT
A1-14	WT WT	WT +C	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT	WT 5	WT -4	-123 -123	+A WT	WT +A	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT
B23-3	WT WT	WT WT	WT -34	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT	WT +A	+A WT	WT -A	WT WT	+A WT	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT
B1-2	WT +T	WT +C	WT -5	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT	+A WT	+A -10/snp	+C WT	+A +C	+T -4	WT -4	-T & snp WT	WT WT	WT WT
C2-19	WT -41	WT WT	WT -4	WT WT	WT WT	WT WT	+C WT/-1	+A +T	-G WT	+T +T	+C -4	Complex deletions	-C WT	WT WT	WT WT

Figure S1: *flo-* mutant genotypes and parameters of the two drought stresses.

A, Genotypes of the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14* *flo-* mutants at the three homeologs of *SVP*, *FLC*, *LHP1*, *TFL1* and *ELF3* as described in Bellec et al., 2022. In each cell, sequenced alleles are presented for the two sgRNAs positions: wild-type (WT) or the indicated mutation; insertions or deletions (– or + nucleotides), single nucleotide polymorphism (snp), and complex deletions. All yellow boxes indicate homozygous mutations in at least one of the sgRNAs position. Light yellow boxes stipulate alleles with no modification of frameshift. B, Diagram representation of the experimental design of the two drought stresses carried before flowering (stress 1) and on flowering plants (stress 2) carried out on the wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14* *flo-* mutants. Stress 2 started on 6 week-old plants for the *flo-* mutants and 8 week-old plants for the wt plants. The black boxes represent the 10-day stress period at 15% soil water content (SWC), the dark grey boxes the water loss between 50% to 15% SWC, the light grey boxes indicate the period when plants were maintained at 50% SWC and the empty boxes, the period when plant were watered in excess (>50% SWC). Stars indicate the mean day to flowering of the different genotypes. C, Percentage of soil water content (SWC) of the control and stress 1 plants. Day 0 indicates the beginning of the loss from 50% to 15% SWC. D, Percentage of wilted plant during the 10-day of stress 1 (day 19 to day 29) in the wt and the *flo-* mutants. E, Percentage of Leaf Water Content (LWC) at day 0 (T0), day 12 day 30 and day 34 of stress 1 carried out on leaf 2, 4, 9 and 12 respectively. Lines indicate the median. Stars show significant differences between control and stress 1 ($p < 0.05$, using ANOVA followed by Tukey’s pairwise multiple comparisons), $n = 3$. F-G, Percentage of wilted plant during the stress 2 in the *flo-* mutant plants (F; day 10 to day 33) and in the wt plants (G; day 23 to day 31). In C and E, # indicate the recovery time point. $n = 10$ to 12

Figure S2: Morphology of the shoot apical meristem of the wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14 flo-* mutants.

Confocal microscopy images of transversal view of the shoot apical meristem of the wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14 flo-* mutants grown under 2, 3, 4 and 5 weeks in long-day conditions. Arrows indicate the presence of leaf primordia. Stars indicate flower in development present on the side of the shoot apical meristem. Hashtags indicate putative axillary meristem in the cauline leaf primordia axis. Ratio in the top left of the images indicate the number of shoot apical meristem observed with this morphology. Scale bar, 100 μ m.

Figure S4: Drought before and after flowering impacted total seed number

Total seed number of wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14* plants in control condition and in response to early drought (stress 1) and drought at flowering (stress 2). Boxes indicate the interquartile range, the vertical line in the middle is the median, the horizontal lines (whiskers) correspond to the highest or lowest value within 1.5 times the interquartile range, letters show significant differences between conditions only ($p < 0.05$, using ANOVA followed by Tukey's pairwise multiple comparisons), $n = 10$ to 12.

Figure S5: Total fatty acid and fatty acid composition showed only few changes in *flo*- mutants in control condition and in response to drought

A, Total fatty acid in mature dry seeds of the wt and the *flo*- mutants (*B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14*) in control condition and in response to drought at flowering (stress 2). B, Principal component analysis (PCA) showing the positions of samples in the plane delineated by component 1 and 2 accounting for 65% of the total variance of the FAs quantified in mature seeds of the wt and the *flo*- mutants (*A1-14*, *A4-14*, *A40-24*, *B1-2*, *B23-3* and *C2-19*) in control condition (triangles) and in response to stress 2 (circles). C-D, Fatty acid composition in $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ (C) and in Mol % (D). In A, C and D, stars indicate significant differences between wt and the *flo*- mutants (*B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14*) ($p < 0.05$, using ANOVA followed by Tukey's pairwise multiple comparisons), $n = 10$ to 12.

Figure S6: Features that showed an increase in accumulation in all the *flo*-mutants upon drought stress (A) Normalized accumulation and (B) structure of the annotated putative metabolite of the eleven features significantly accumulated in mature dry seeds upon drought stress (indicated with a red star on figure 4B). In A, boxes indicate the interquartile range, the vertical line in the middle is the median, the horizontal lines (whiskers) correspond to the highest or lowest value within 1.5 times the interquartile range, $n = 3$.

Figure S7: The seed specialized metabolome of the *A1-14* and *A4-12 flo-* mutants showed a constitutive wt stress response while the specialized metabolome of the *C2-19* and the *B23-3 flo-* mutants showed a wt control response upon drought stress.

Hierarchical clustering dendrogram of the 202 features significantly regulated in control condition compared to stress in wt (indicated with a black star on Figure 4B).

Figure S9: Metabolite families and family groups from total annotated features and the features differentially accumulated across genotypes (wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14 flo-* mutants) in mature seeds and vegetative leaves

A, Percentage of the metabolite families in the 851 (49%) annotated features of the 1739 total features quantified in mature seeds (left) and in the 364 (50%) annotated features of the 725 features identified differentially accumulated in mature seeds across genotypes (wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14 flo-* mutants; right). B, Percentage of the metabolite family group in the 732 (42%) annotated features of the 1739 total features quantified in mature seeds (left) and in the 315 (43%) annotated features of the 725 features identified differentially accumulated in mature seeds across genotypes (wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14 flo-* mutants; right). C, Percentage of the metabolite families in the 545 (60%) annotated features of the 913 total features quantified in vegetative leaves (left) and in the 84 (64%) annotated features of the 132 features identified differentially accumulated in vegetative leaves across genotypes (wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14 flo-* mutants; right). D, Percentage of the metabolite family group in the 464 (51%) annotated features of the 913 total features quantified in vegetative leaves (left) and in the 77 (58%) annotated features of the 132 features identified differentially accumulated in vegetative leaves across genotypes (wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14 flo-* mutants; right).

Figure S10: Hierarchical clustering of metabolomic data of the wt and the *B1-2*, *C2-19*, *A40-24*, *B23-3*, *A4-12* and *A1-14 flo-* mutants showed different groups in seeds and leaves.

A, Heat map representing the hierarchical clustering of the 725 significantly regulated features in the mature dry seeds grown in control condition. B, Heat map representing the hierarchical clustering of the 132 significantly regulated features in vegetative leaves.

Figure S11: Flowering time and seed yield of the natural accessions with various flowering times

A, Picture of 58 day-old wt (Celine) and the CAM221, L2F4, CN101981, CAM151, CAM203 additional genotypes. Bar, 15-cm.

B, Days to flowering (days to the first flower open) of wt (Celine), CAM221, L2F4, CN101981, CAM151 and CAM203. The dotted line indicates the flowering time of the wt (Celine). Boxes indicate the interquartile range, the vertical line in the middle is the median, the horizontal lines (whiskers) correspond to the highest or lowest value within 1.5 times the interquartile range, letters show significant differences between genotypes ($p < 0.05$, using ANOVA followed by Tukey's pairwise multiple comparisons), $n = 10$ to 12